

Feeding behavior of green leafhopper (GLH) on rice varieties resistant to rice tungro

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Viruliferous GLH *Nephotettix virescens* insects were allowed to feed on rice cultures and varieties and their feeding from phloem/xylem ascertained by the quality of honeydew (acidic or basic) excreted. Insects that feed on phloem content excrete honeydew with basic properties that caused blue patches in bromocresol-treated filter paper. Insects that feed on xylem content excrete honeydew with acidic properties that caused brown or orange spots.

Basic honeydew excretion was higher in rice varieties that were more severely infected by tungro (see table). This indicates that the insect vector had fed on the phloem content of varieties susceptible to RTV.

Among the cultures tested, IR33043-46-1-3 showed the lowest tungro infection and had no GLH feeding on the phloem. ■

Honeydew excretion of viruliferous GLH feeding on different rice varieties. ^a

Variety	Tungro infection (%)	Area of basic honeydew spots (mm ²)	Area of acidic honeydew spots (mm ²)
IR72	20.00	12 b	219 hij
IR33043-46-1-3	20.00	0 a	228 lm
IR50404-57-2-2-3	30.00	17 bcd	226 klm
IR52431-60-1-2-1	20.00	19 cde	220 hij
IR34686-56-2-2-2	30.00	17 bcd	223 ijkl
CRM25	30.00	20 cdef	221 hijk
TNAULFR84278	30.00	17 bcd	230 mn
AS33773	30.00	25 f	225 klm
IR32429-148-13-3	20.00	23 ef	224 jke
IR37865-29-3-1-3	30.00	22 def	239 o
IR39357-91-3-2-3	20.00	21 def	218 hi
TNAU831520	30.00	31 g	217 b
TNAU831521	20.00	17 bcd	230 mn
IR50	20.00	15 bc	234 n
IR64	30.00	16 bc	223 ijkl
ASD17	30.00	30 g	211 g
MDU3	50.00	130 f	135 f
Ponni	40.00	108 h	137 f
White Ponni	50.00	124 j	124 e
IR20	70.00	170 m	88 c
CO 37	80.00	162 l	98 d
CO 43	70.00	153 k	92 c
ADT36	80.00	184 n	76 b
ADT38	60.00	165 l	91 c
TNI (susceptible check)	90.00	245 o	30 a

^a Means of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by same letter are not significant different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

Stress tolerance – excess water

Screening of advanced rice lines against natural flooding

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We screened 60 advanced breeding lines for submergence tolerance in 1989 wet season. The test cultivars and check FR13A were seeded in three 3-m-long rows. The first flooding was on 30 Jul; the field remained inundated until 7 Aug. Peak water depth was 60 cm; 45-50 cm water was maintained for 6 d.

Plant height of advanced lines ranged from 12 to 22 cm; FR13A was 25 cm tall. Submergence tolerance was scored after the flood receded and regeneration ability, 7 d after water recession.

Among the advanced lines, 6 scored 5, 28 scored 7, and 26 scored 9. IR43439-99-23-1-1, IR56723-1, and IR313228-474-3P had excellent regeneration ability; IR59037-1, IR57741, IR43470-7-3-5-1, and IR46292-24-2-2-1-2 had good regeneration ability (see table).

In the second flood 20-31 Aug, maximum water depth was 58 cm. Plant heights ranged from 28 to 36 cm. The two best entries were IR43439-99-23-1-1 and IR56723-1.

Entries with regeneration ability scores 1 and 3 should be useful for flood-prone areas where fields are flooded at the early vegetative stage for 1 wk or longer. ■

Submergence tolerance and regeneration ability of various promising rainfed lowland lines. 1989.

Promising advanced line or cultivar	First flood ^a (30 Jul-8 Aug)			Second flood ^a (20-31 Aug)			Grain yield (g/plot)
	Plant ht (cm)	Submergence score ^b	Regeneration ability	Plant (ht)	Submergence score ^b	Regeneration ability	
IR43439-99-23-1-1	12	5	1	35	1	1	400
IR56723-1	14	5	1	34	1	1	380
IR59037-1	11	5	3	32	3	1	490
IR313228-474-3P	16	5	1	36	3	3	600
IR57741	15	5	3	28	7	1	300
IR43470-7-3-5-1	13	5	3	34	5	1	420
IR46292-24-2-2-1-2	17	5	3	36	3	3	700
FR13A	25	1	1	45	1	1	210

^a Age of seedlings at first flooding was 13 d; at second flooding, 26 d. ^b Scale for submergence and recovery: 1 = 90-100%, 3 = 70-89%, 5 = 50-69%, 7 = 30-49%, 9 = less than 30%.